

AIJACLA

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs

Vol. 1

January, 2021

About the Journal

An International,
Double-blind,
Peer-reviewed and
Annually published
Journal.

Contact Details

Email:

aequitasvictoria@gmail.com

Helpline Number:

8473808112

Office Address:

H/o Shri Sarthak Aryan,
C/o Shri Subodh Kumar,
Old Madhya Bihar Gramin
Bank Building,
Sakurabad
P.O.: Sakurabad,
Dist: Jehanabad,
PIN: 804425 (Bihar).

Published By

**Aequitas Victoria
Foundation**

www.aequivic.in

AEQUITAS VICTORIA FOUNDATION PRESENTS
ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ANALYSIS OF CONTEMPORARY
LEGAL AFFAIRS

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs (AIJACLA) is an annual international double-blind peer-reviewed journal in the field of law. The journal deals with contemporary affairs primarily within the discipline of law but also encourages interdisciplinary research works from any discipline provided the relation of the subject-matter with the legal institutions, legal instruments, or any other legal matters shall be established and highlighted to meet the eligibility criteria of the journal.

Broadly the Journal welcomes research works from each branch of law like: Human Rights, Humanitarian Rights, IPR, Environmental Law, Public and Private International Law, Air and Space Law, Drone Law, Martial Law, Sports Law, Fashion Law, etc. It even encourages contributions from panel discussion or conference reports based on the topics of recent developments in the field of law. Further, case commentaries, law book reviews, legislative and policy analysis are also welcomed. The journal will also publish contributions that are not expressly from the discipline of law but establishes a relation with any of the legal matters and gives it an interdisciplinary character.

However, comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws.

SCOPE

The scope of this journal extends to the entire world transcending all national boundaries of the States. It is an international journal aimed at establishing a global network of research and analysis in the field of law. The medium of publication will be primarily **American English** subject to the majority opinion of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, and the Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee.

The Journal is expected to be a globally open accessed journal subject to the technical limitations and international or regional laws in force or existence anywhere either internationally or nationally.

The journal intends to cover all fields of law including-

1. International Conventions passed by International or Global Bodies;
2. Regional Conventions, Rules, Policies, etc. passed by Regional Organizations that are recognized globally;
3. Rules, Policies, By-laws, etc. passed by any Inter-state bodies provided such matters influence the relationship between two or more countries that are recognized as sovereign under the international rules;
4. Any other Conventions, Laws, Rules, etc. that are not directly recognized by any international or global bodies or agencies but are going to influence or has an impact on the diplomatic relationships between two or more countries;
5. Cases decided by International Adjudicating Authorities;
6. Any Laws, By-laws, Enactments, Policies, etc. passed by a proper legislative authority, competent courts, authorities with proper legal recognitions in any sovereign country;
7. Conference, Seminar, Colloquium, etc. reports that are based on topics of law;
8. Lectures from eminent professionals in the field of law, or lectures on legal topics from eminent personalities;
9. Researches made on Theories relevant to the field of Law;
10. Any researchable topic from any discipline provided the subject-matter of such research shall properly establish the nexus with the legal institutions, instruments, or any other subject-matter of law; and
11. Results of researches carried out independently either as an individual, group, or as an organization in the field of law.

However, the journal shall not publish any material related to the following either in whole or in part subject to the approval of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee-

1. Comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws;
2. Political opinions even if based on legal topics that are suspected of influencing voting behavior of the citizens of any sovereign country against the provisions of an established legislations either international, regional, or local, or is expected to incite rebellion or conflict against any popularly established government; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee;
3. Any discriminatory opinions regarding racial, gender, or any other class of people, or comments in favor of any particular group, institution, organization, party, community, etc.; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee; or
4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

BOARD OF EDITORS

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. (Dr) Chintamani Rout

HOD. Department of Law
North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong

Senior Editor

Prof. (Dr) Yugal Kishore

Professor of Law, ICFAI Law School,
ICFAI University Dehradun, Former
Professor, Registrar, Vice-Chancellor
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Senior Editor

Dr. Heru Susetyo

Assistant professor, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Chairman of the Center for Islam and
Islamic Law, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Senior Editor

Mrs. Ronaldah Lerato Karabo Ozah

Director- Litigation, Research and
Advocacy and Lecturer, Centre for
Child Law, University of Pretoria, South
Africa.

Senior Editor

Dr Dhruvajyoti Das

Associate Professor, Department of
English, Cotton University

Senior Editor

Dr. Sachin Ghimire

Medical Anthropologist and Filmmaker
Assistant professor, Department of
Public health, Manamohan Memorial
Institute of Health Sciences(MMIHS),
Kathmandu, Nepal.

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Dr. Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor, University Law
College Gauhati University

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Dharmashastra
National Law University, Jodhpur

Associate Editors

Ms. Moushita Dutta

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Mrs. Mageswary Siva Subramaniam

Lecturer with Faculty of Law,
Multimedia University (Malacca
Campus), Malacca, Malaysia.
Visiting lecturer, Lingnan University,
Hong Kong

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Family Law,
Dharmashastra National Law University
(DNLU), Jabalpur.

Mrs. Rima Borthakur

Former Senior Manager, Document
Review department in Thomson Reuters
(Pangea3), New York City.

Associate Editors

Mr. Prithvi Raaj Choudhury

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Associate Editors

Mr. Amey Pandey

Co-Founder CLAT Junction, Working
with Safe in India Foundation

EXPERT COMMITTEE

**Prof (Dr) Bhaskar Kumar
Chakravarty**

Visiting Professor of Law Royal Global
University, Former Professor Dean and
Head Department of Law, Gauhati
University, Founder Head of
Department of Law, Tezpur University

Dr Gautami Dutta

Principal R.K.B. Law College

Dr Anup Kumar Ray

Principal, Goalpara Law College

Prof (Dr) Atul Chandra Talukdar

Dean School of Social Science &
Humanities, University of Science &
Technology Meghalaya

Dr Ajay Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Dr Md. Sultan Haidar Alam

Principal NERIM Law College

Dr Kasturi Gakul

Assistant Professor of Law
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Dr Bimal Kumar Baishya

Associate Professor (Rtd.), University
Law College Gauhati University

Dr Sujata Bhattacharyya

Principal Nowgong Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Editor Nyaijyoti, All Assam Lawyers
Association

REVIEW COMMITTEE

Mrs. Dimpy Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashmi Gogoi

Research Scholar Gauhati University
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Mrs. Karishma Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Darshana Deepak Das

MA in English Litt (Specialization in
Indian Literature), PGT in Potential and
Concept Academy, Working as an SME
in AMF Edu Solutions
Designation: Member Content

Suyash Pranay Tripathi

PGDCPLP, National Law School of
India University Bangalore, LLM
National Law University, Odisha
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Anya Behera

LLM from National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB from
KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashi Gupta

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB
Vivekananda Institute of Professional
Studies, New Delhi
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Alekh

LLM, National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Srishti

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Aadya Ambastha
Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Ishan Mishra

Student
ICFAI Law College, Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Assessment Committee

Girisha Sinha

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Prachi Prem

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Monalisa Choudhury

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Ishan Mishra
Student at ICFAI University Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Pranay Rathore

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Riya Kumari

Student at University Law College,
Hazaribagh
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Shreya Gupta

Student at JIMS Engineering
Management Technical Campus, Noida
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Prachi Nayan

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB, ICFAI
Law School, Dehradun
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Saloni Sharma

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Bomkesh Mandal

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Riya Sharma
Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Basuri Poddar

Student at National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

CORE TEAM (MANAGING COMMITTEE)

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary

Ms Vidisha Dixit

Hon'ble Member

Mrs Pranati Boruah

Hon'ble President

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Hon'ble Member (Founder)

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Hon'ble Member

Mr Sarthak Aryan

Hon'ble Member (Co-Founder)

ADMINISTRATIVE SECTION

Executive Committee

Chief Executive Officer

Ms Kashmiri Khanam

Assistant Professor, Dhubri Law
College, Research Scholar, Central
University of Haryana

Executive Officer

Ms Saloni Sharma

Fairfield Institute of Management and
Technology, New Delhi
Executive Officer

Ms Darshee Madhukallya

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Content Designer

Ms Abhishree Kashay

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Basnuri Poddar

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Gautami Chakravarty

KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar

Executive Officer

Ms Riya Kumari

University Law College, Hazaribagh

Content designer

Bonaini Deori

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Ms Nijhum Roy

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Puja Bardhan

West Guwahati Commerce College

Event Manager

Ms Nargis Choudhury

Former Lecturer, School of Law and
Judicial Sciences, Apex Professional
University, Arunachal Pradesh

Executive Officer

Mr Chetan Anand Mahapatra

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Shreya Gupta

JIS Engineering Management Technical
Campus, Noida

Content Designer

Ms Dikshita Nanda Nath

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Mr Arunabh Chakravarty

Department of English, Gauhati
University

Event Manager

Mr Debanjan Das

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Disciplinary Committee

Chairman

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Rtd. Police Officer, Assam Police
Hon'ble Member Managing Committee,
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Former Assistant Professor NERIM
Law College, Advocate Gauhati High
Court and Research Scholar North-
Eastern Hill University, Hon'ble
Member The Managing Committee
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Advocate Rajendra Singh

Suryavanshi

Advocate, Supreme Court of India

Grievance Redressal Committee

Chairman

Dr Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor
University Law College Gauhati
University

Dr Ajoy Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Member, All Assam Lawyers
Association

Mrs Roseleen Deori

Assistant Professor
Nowgaong Law College

VOLUME 1
(Editorial Special Issue)
2020

AJACLA

Ms Vidisha Dixit
Hon'ble Member The Managing
Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Media Cell

Mrs Kangkana Goswami
Assistant Editor NE News

Mr Sandeep Deo
Founder, India Speaks Daily
Mrs Prity Deka
Assistant Manager, Axis Bank

Mr Bishaldeep Kakoti
Founder, The Youths Mind

IT Section

Ishita Gupta

United College of Engineering and
Research, Prayagraj

Mr Sarthak Aryan

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam, Hon'ble Member The
Managing Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SI No.	Title of Papers and Names and Designations of Authors	Page No.
SECTION A: RESEARCH PAPERS		
1	Affirmative Principle: Making, Breaking and Shaking (MBS) Approach of Judiciary <i>-Dr Rangswami D, Assistant Professor of Law, Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, Karnataka</i>	1 - 17
2	Clinical and Continuing Legal Education- Interface for Confidence Building Between Law Students and Legal Professionals in Contemporary India <i>- Dr. Md. Sultan Haidar Alam, Principal, NERIM Law College</i>	18 - 29
3	A Critical Appraisal of the Legal Service Authorities Act with Special Reference to Lok Adalat <i>- Dr. Dhiraj Bhusan Sarmah, Former Faculty of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University & Dr. Plabita Saikia, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	30 - 49
4	Establishment of DNA Data Bank in India: A Legal Analysis <i>- Dr. Ranjit Sil, Assistant Professor, Department Of Law, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong</i>	50 - 64
5	Ecocentric Approaches of the Restorative Justice Theory Vis-à-vis the Legal Issues of Civil and Criminal Liability of the Baghjan Blowout Case in Assam <i>- Dr. Matiur Rahman, Assistant Professor of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University</i>	65 - 76
6	A Comparative Study on Secondary Patenting on Pharmaceutical: Striking A Balance Between Competition Law and IPR <i>- Dr. Kakumani Katakya, Faculty of Law Gauhati University</i>	77 - 90
7	Community and Environmental Protection- - In Search of the Lost Spring of Happiness of the North-Eastern Region <i>- Dr. Sujata Bhattacharyya, Principal, Nowgong Law College</i>	91 - 106
8	National Emergency: A Comparative Analysis of Emergency Laws in India USA and Germany <i>- Abhishek Kumar Khaund, Advocate. Gauhati High Court</i>	107 - 124
9	Legal Frameworks Relating to Use of Pesticides on Horticultural Activities Vis-à-vis Climate Change <i>- Bonani Deori, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Mritunjoy Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	125 -145
20	The Arms Act, 1959: A Legal Analysis and Comparative Study with USA <i>- Bikash Sen Deka, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	146 -168
11	Comparative Study on Intergovernmental Tax Immunities under the Federal Constitutions of Australia, Canada, India and USA <i>- Bandita Das, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	169 - 177
12	Unlawful Activities and Prevention Act: Balancing National Security with Citizen's Rights <i>- Girisha Sinha, Research Assistant under Advocate Ritesh Kumar Patna High Court</i>	178 - 191
13	An Analysis of the Legal Framework of the Co-operative Banks in India	192 - 215

	- Bidikha Gogoi, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
14	Parole- The Reformative Instrument of Punishment in Prisonization	216 -228
	- Nayana Medhi, Former Faculty of Law, Indraprastha University	
15	Assam Police and Its Organizational Structure	229 - 271
	- Dr. Anup Kr. Ray, Principal, Goalpara Law College	
SECTION B: ARTICLES		
16	Anti-Defection Law: A Conflict Between the Right to Dissent and the Integrity of the Political Party	273 - 281
	- Apurva Mehta, B.A. LL.B. (Criminal Law Hons.), 5th Year, National University of Study and Research in Law, Ranchi	
17	Contempt of Court: An Urgent Requisite to Re-Explore	282 - 287
	- Paras Gupta, B.A.LL.B.(Hons.), Institute of Law, Kurukshetra University	
18	Lack of Uniform Code of Conduct to Address the Judges in India	288 - 294
	- Saloni Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology & Riya Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology	
19	Rejuvenating the Right to Equality and Life under the Paradigm of Transformative Constitution	295 - 301
	- Dr. Daisy Changmai, Faculty of Law, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam, Former Principal of Dibrugarh Hanumanbux Surojmal Kanoi Law College	
20	Genital Mutilation- An Appeal for Legislative Response in India to Outlaw the Menace	302 - 311
	- Dr. Karavi Barman, Assistant Professor, N.E.F Law College, Guwahati	
21	Surrogacy in India: A Legal Perspective	312 - 319
	- Dr. Shrutimala Goswami, Assistant Professor, NERIM Law College & Arunav Barua., Research Scholar, Assam Don Bosco University	
22	Merger and Amalgamation of Companies in India: AN Analysis of Its Impact on Various Stakeholders	320 - 330
	- Purbaja Sarmah, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
23	Human Rights Crisis amongst IDPs in Assam: Issues and Challenges	331 - 337
	- Dr. Gautami Dutta, Principal, Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Dibrugarh	
24	Protective Discrimination under the Constitution of India	338 -345
	- Pallabi Nath, LL.M 1 st Semester, Tezpur University	
25	Mob Lynching as a New Offence Emerging in India: A Study with a Special Reference to Assam	346 - 355
	- Nargis Choudhury, Former Faculty of Legal Studies, School of Law and Juridical Sciences Apex Professional University, Pasighat, Arunachal Pradesh	
26	The Doctrine of Pious Obligation and Its Relevance under the Hindu Law in the Present Time	356 - 363
	-Titikhya Barkataki, LL.M, 1st Semester, Gauhati University	
27	COVID-19 Pandemic: Justice Demands for Increasing Deterrence in India	364 - 370

- Jayanta Boruah, Research Scholar, North-Eastern Hill University, Former Assistant Professor of Law & Advocate & Sarthak Aryan, BALLB (3rd Year) National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam

SECTION C: LEGAL ESSAYS

- 28 **Traditional Ecological Knowledge and Biological Diversity Act, 2002: A Critical Analysis** 371 - 378
- Dr. Ravi Kanta Mishra, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, North-Eastern Hill University
- 29 **Trial by Media: A Hindrance in the Path of Justice and Fairness** 379 - 384
- Bidisha Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Kaustabh Moni Sarma, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 30 **Payment of Rent in Commercial Lease Contracts in Context of the COVID Crisis** 385 -391
- Clarissa D'Lima, Student Kirit P. Mehta School of Law, NMIMS Deemed-to-be University, Mumbai
- 31 **Adultery was Never a Crime: It is a Moral Wrong** 392 - 397
- Aadarsh Kumar Shrivastava, B.A.LL.B. 10th semester, Government New Law College Indore MP
- 32 **The Legal Protection for Consumers in Conducting E-Commerce Activities in India** 398 - 403
- Dikshita Nanda, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 33 **"Rarest of Rare Case"- Capital Punishment** 404 - 408
- Devika Warriar, Bharata Mata School of Legal Studies, Kerala
- 34 **Mob Lynching in India: A Threat to Mankind** 409 -413
- Nabanita Baruah, Student (BALLB 7th Sem), Department of Law, NERIM Law College
- 35 **Biomedical Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic in India** 414 - 418
- Farzin Naz, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 36 **Impact of Lockdown on Migrant Workers whether a Humanitarian or Human Rights Crisis?** 419 - 426
- Nikhil Moitra, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam
- 37 **Right to Privacy and Data Protection Law in India with a Brief Comparative Analysis with UK and USA** 427 - 433
- Bandana Saikia, Student, Symbiosis Law School Pune
- 38 **Rise of Pedophiles amidst Coronavirus Outbreak** 434 - 440
- Bulbul Kumari, Student, Dharmashastra National Law University, Jabalpur
- 39 **Arrest of Tax Evaders under the Central Goods and Service Tax Act 2017** 441 - 446
- Hunseng Tungkhang, Student, NERIM Law College

SECTION D: CASE COMMENTARY

- 40 **M/S. Nandhini Deluxe v. M/S. Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers Federation Ltd** 447 - 454
- Natesh Kumar, B.COM; LL.B.(HONS.), School of Law, SASTRA Deemed University
- 41 **The Interpretation of the Law of Limitation by the Indian Supreme Court during the COVID-19 Pandemic** 455 - 457
- Dr. Smarita Mohanty, Member, State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, Odisha
- 42 **Vineeta Sharma v. Rakesh Sharma** 458 - 460

	- <i>Namrata Chakrabarty, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	
43	Dunlop Pneumatic Tyre Co. Ltd. V. Selfridge & Co. Ltd.	461 - 463
	- <i>Chetna Priyam, BA LLB (Hons.), ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	
44	Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India	464 - 467
	- <i>Sristi Ray, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Kanika Chugh, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
45	Ashok Kumar Kalra v. Surendra Agnihotori (SLP No. 23599 of 2018)	468 - 470
	- <i>Monalisa Choudhury, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
46	Committee of Creditors Essar Steel India Limited Through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors.	471 - 475
	- <i>Rajat Gupta, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Vaishnavi Pandey, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
SECTION E: LEGISLATIVE ANALYSIS		
47	Relevance of Narcotics Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPs) Act, 1985	476 - 480
	- <i>Shivangi Pandey, LL.B.(CONST. LAW SPZ.) (5th Year), University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun</i>	
48	Analysis of the Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Bill, 2020	481 - 485
	- <i>Masia Baruah, Student BALLB 6th Semester, NERIM Law College</i>	
SECTION F: BOOK REVIEW		
49	Just Mercy: A Story of Justice and Redemption	486 - 487
	- <i>Aniket Jadhav, Student, Government Law College, Mumbai</i>	
50	Book Review on Judiciary, Judges and Administration of Justice	488 - 489
	- <i>Ishan Mishra, Student, ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	

SECTION (C) LEGAL ESSAY

BIOMEDICAL WASTE MANAGEMENT DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN
INDIA

Section:	C
Category:	Legal Essay
Paper Code:	LE-FN-13
Page Number:	414 - 418
Date of Publication:	February 10, 2021
Citation:	Farzin Naz, Biomedical Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic in India, 1, AJACLA, 414, 414-418, (2021).

DETAILS OF AUTHOR(S)

Farzin Naz

Advocate

Gauhati High Court

Email id: nazfarzin7@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

What we are currently facing is an unexpected and turbulent change. This pandemic has locked crores of people in their homes, closed service organizations, and brought everything to a halt. Covid-19 is of recent origin. During this time, safe disposal of medical waste generated from examination and treatment of Covid-19 patients effectively is a must to protect the health of the people. Therefore, in this article, an attempt is made for understanding the challenges which India is facing at present and to suggest some measures which can be adopted for the proper disposal of biomedical waste.

KEYWORDS

Covid-19, Pandemic, Waste, Epidemic, Treatment, Disposal.

INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus generally belongs to the family of Viruses commonly known as “*Coronaviridae*” and it derives its name from the Latin word “*Corona*” which means Crown. They are found in both animals as well as in human beings and can cause severe respiratory diseases in humans like “*Severe Acute*”

“*Respiratory Syndrome*” also known as SARS. A new strain was identified recently and was named “*nCov*”. As it was identified in the year 2019, hence it has been referred to as “*Covid-19*”¹. The first case of Covid-19 was detected in the city of Wuhan in China in December 2019. It was further declared as a

¹ Anurag Bortahkur, Coronavirus and India, A.T, March, 19, 2020.

Public Health Emergency by the World Health Organization in January 2020 and later was termed as pandemic. As compared to earlier outbreaks of SARS, COVID-19 has affected the entire globe and has spread in almost every continent. As the cases continue to rise in India, the amount of waste generated during Treatment/Diagnosis/Quarantine of Covid-19 Patients is increasing day by day. Besides controlling the pandemic, the Government is facing another issue i.e., safe and scientific disposal of biomedical waste. At present, India is producing about 2, 00,000 tonnes of waste p.a. Increase in biomedical waste in the city of Pune has resulted in the breakdown of the city's only incinerator for treating bio-medical wastes². This shows that the Government has to take up necessary steps and follow proper disposal methods to prevent the spread of infection.

CHARACTERISTICS OF BIOMEDICAL WASTES GENERATED DURING COVID-19

Wastes generated during Treatment/Diagnosis/Quarantine of COVID-19 Patients includes Human Anatomical, Disinfectants, Discarded bed sheets, mattresses, blood, body fluids, Sharps, gloves, masks, gowns as well as other Recyclable wastes. As per WHO Guideline³, the

² Umesh Ishalkar, Covid-19 waste surge breakdown incinerator, T.O.I, Jun, 2020, 15.

³ Water, Sanitation, hygiene and Waste Management for COVID-19 virus, World Health Organization, (Jun. 2020, 28, AM),

wastes generated are highly infectious and must be properly disposed of. Such wastes are to be pre-treated and disposed of by Wastes Collectors. As the amount of discarded PPE will increase during the pandemic, thus it is suggested that additional treatment plants are to be set up and alternative techniques should be adopted for handling wastes. For water generated from washing PPE, Gloves, and Reusable aprons, it is recommended that it should be cleaned by using soap and water and then should be decontaminated using sodium hypochlorite solution. All single-use gloves and gowns are not to be reused as they are highly infectious.

A recent study on the surface stability of the virus shows that the deadly virus can survive up to 72 hours on materials like plastic and stainless steel and concerning copper surfaces, it can last only up to 4 hours. Thus, the immediate environment surrounding an infected person can be a good source for the spread of infection. Currently, the studies have not proved the spread of the virus from the feces of infected persons.

CENTRAL POLLUTION CONTROL BOARD'S GUIDELINES ON MANAGEMENT OF COVID-19 WASTES

https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/331846/WHO-2019-nCoV-IPC_WASH-2020.3-eng.pdf.

In April 2020, CPCB⁴ came up with a detailed guideline on handling and management of biomedical wastes generated from the treatment of Covid Patients. These guidelines have to be followed along with the Biomedical Wastes Management Rules of 2016. It has specified the duties of all the stakeholders concerning scientific management and disposal of biomedical waste at times of Covid pandemic. The guidelines are as follows:

I. Isolation Wards:

Wastes generated from isolated wards at quarantine centers are to be kept in double-layered, color-coded bags and containers. Such bags should be properly labeled as “Covid-19”, for better identification of Covid wastes. Diapers containing Faeces of patients should be kept in yellow bags; used PPE should be collected in red bags and masks should be kept in yellow bags.

II. Duties of operators of CBWTF:

Operators are under duty to provide adequate PPE to all the workers and report about the amount of collection of wastes to the concerned Pollution Control Boards from time to time. Properly

sanitize the vehicle used for collecting Covid wastes.

III. Duties of Pollution Control Boards/Committees:

All the concerned authorities have to maintain records of several wards and quarantine centers, in the respective States. To ensure that wastes are properly collected and disposed of as per the BMW Rules of 2016 and CPCB’s guidelines.

IV. Duties of Local Bodies:

Furnish a report about collection and disposal of wastes generated from quarantine centers to the concerned Pollution Control Board or Pollution Control Committees. Further, they are to assist the CBWTF by providing authorization and support to the concerned staff of CBWTF.

WASTE CRISIS

India is fighting with another bigger problem, along with the COVID-19 pandemic, i.e it is facing a waste crisis. Masks, gloves, PPE Kits, gowns, headgears, quarantine wastes including bed sheets and used quilt, laboratory wastes, etc. after use, ends up creating a huge amount of wastes. The discarded wastes contain almost all types of wastes like human anatomical waste, plastic wastes, and sharps. Over growing amount of wastes has resulted in

⁴ Guidelines for Handling, Treatment and Disposal of Waste Generated during Treatment/Diagnosis/Quarantine of COVID-19 Patients, Central Pollution Control Board (Ministry Of Environment, Forest And Climate Change), (Aug. 2020, 31, 10:00 AM), https://tnpcb.gov.in/pdf_2020/BMW-GUIDELINES-COVID_Revised_April2020.pdf.

overflowing of landfills, breaking up incinerators, etc. These wastes pose a serious threat to sanitation workers and rag pickers. Although guidelines have been laid down for providing proper PPE Kits, boots, and masks to all the sanitation workers, who are at a high risk of getting infected, it is evident that they are handling these wastes by only wearing masks.⁵ In a recent report from Mumbai's Common Biomedical Waste Treatment Facility, near about 600kg of wastes in form of discarded masks and gloves ends up in landfills instead of proper incinerating sites as people are not segregating domestic wastes properly. To date, about 80 sanitation workers have tested positive, out of which 25 workers have died.⁶ Moreover, there is a suspicion amongst the scientists that Covid-19 can even affect animals since a tiger named Nadia in New York was alleged to have contracted with coronavirus from humans and similarly several other cases where both wild and domestic animals were alleged to have contracted with the virus.⁷ As such if Covid-19 wastes are not disposed of properly and are left open then it might even affect the animals in the concerned environment. India in total only has 198 Common Bio-Medical Waste Treatment Facilities (CBMWTs)

CONCLUSION

During this pandemic, if bio-medical wastes generated during treatment and testing of Covid-19 patients are not disposed of properly then there will arise a major possibility of community spreading of this virus, which already has created a lot of issues in the health administration of the Nation. It is therefore required that more awareness regarding waste disposal shall be spread through various mediums where even NGOs as well as other organizations or individuals can participate in assisting the respective governments. It is not the time to criticize the government for not being able to manage such a huge amount of wastes, since even if the government machinery fails to address the issue due to lack of administration, yet we all will have to suffer the consequences which we are already suffering. Thus, besides criticizing the administration, it's the responsibility of the social media also to aware the ignorant citizens of the measures they should take for proper disposal of such wastes. Arrangements shall

⁵ Jayashree Nandi, India stares at biomedical crisis, H.T, Jun. 2020, 23.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Helen Davidson, Hong Kong warns residents not to kiss pets after dog contracts coronavirus, The Guardian, (Sep. 2020, 05, 03:54 PM), <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/05/hong-kong-warns-residents-not-to-kiss-pets-after-dog-contracts-coronavirus>.

be made by every citizen for disposing of their household wastes within their campus or locality itself through safe measures so that transportation of such wastes can be reduced. Those wastes that cannot be disposed of within one's campus shall be segregated and properly isolated in a safe place so that the virus could die. These measures will reduce the burden on the municipal corporations which will allow them to focus more on disposing of those wastes that are generated during the treatment of Covid-19 wastes. Separate chambers shall be constructed at alternative places where bio-medical wastes from quarantine centers, Covid-19 laboratory clinics as well as hospitals can be kept in isolation for seven days alternatively in different chambers in isolation for allowing the virus to die before disposal. However, the areas where such chambers will be constructed must be isolated from all kinds of humans, animals, or even birds.